

Kinetics of Oxidation of Acetophenones by Selenium Dioxide[†]

N. D. VALECHHA*

Chemistry Department, Government Science College, Rewa-486 001

and

J. P. SEWANEE

Chemistry Department, Government P. G. College, Satna-485 001

Manuscript received 16 February 1984, revised 1 July 1986, accepted 30 October 1986

The kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone by selenium dioxide in 70% (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture have been investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to selenium dioxide and approximately first order with respect to acetophenone. The oxidation reactions are catalysed by sulphuric acid. The primary salt effect is nominal retarding. The reaction rate increases with increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture. The observed order of reactivity among acetophenones studied is *p*-CH₃>H>*p*-Cl. Activation parameters have been evaluated. On the basis of experimental facts, a suitable mechanism has been proposed.

SELENIUM dioxide has been used as an oxidising agent in the kinetic study of oxidation of some ketones¹⁻⁵. Similar studies with acetophenones are lacking. However, the oxidation of acetophenones by a number of oxidants⁶⁻¹⁵ have received a considerable attention from the kinetic and mechanistic point of view. This prompted us to investigate the kinetics of oxidation of acetophenones by selenium dioxide. In this paper, the results of kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone by selenium dioxide are reported.

Experimental

Selenium dioxide (Loba), acetophenone (B.D.H.), *p*-methylacetophenone (Fluka, A.G.), *p*-chloroacetophenone (Fluka, A.G.) and acetic acid (S. Merck) were used. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Selenium dioxide solution was prepared in distilled water and was standardised iodometrically. The kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The rate of reaction was determined by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide at known intervals of time by iodimetric⁴ method. Since ionic strength has nearly no effect on the reaction rate, it has not been kept constant.

Stoichiometry and products: The stoichiometry of the reactions were determined by allowing the reaction mixture containing excess of selenium dioxide (10 times) over acetophenone at 65° until there was no change in the selenium dioxide concentration. It was observed that one mole of acetophenone requires one mole of selenium dioxide for

complete oxidation. The stoichiometric equation can be written as

The product analysis shows the formation of phenyl glyoxals identified either by preparing phenyl hydrazones¹⁶ or isolating as phenyl glyoxal hydrates^{16,17}.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of reaction on reactants: The variation in selenium dioxide concentration (Table 1) showed that the order of reaction in selenium dioxide is one. The pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the integrated first order equation. The rate constants were calculated with an accuracy of 1-2% in duplicate kinetic runs.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SELENIUM DIOXIDE CONCENTRATION

[Acetophenone]=0.80 M, HOAc-water=70/30 (v/v)	Temp.=338 K,	10 ⁸ [SeO ₂] M	10 ⁸ k/s ⁻¹	4.0	8.0	10.0	12.0	16.0
a	7.00	6.95	6.95	6.91	6.91			
b	8.39	8.38	8.36	8.17	8.12			
c	5.53	5.52	5.42	5.42	5.40			

a=acetophenone, b=*p*-CH₃-acetophenone, c=*p*-Cl-acetophenone.

The variation in acetophenone concentration showed that the pseudo-first order rate constant in selenium dioxide increases with increase in the concentration of acetophenone (Table 2). The plots of

[†] Part of the paper presented at 22nd Annual Convention of Chemists, 1985.

log k vs log [acetophenones] are linear having slopes of 1.11, 1.25 and 1.28 for acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone, respectively, indicating the order of reactions with respect to acetophenones under investigation is not strictly unity. This fact probably suggests the formation of intermediate between substrate and the oxidising species. Further the plots of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ are linear with no intercepts, showing the intermediates formed are unstable, that is, their formation constants are too low to be kinetically determined.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACETOPHENONE CONCENTRATION
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01\text{ M}$, Temp. = 338 K, HOAc - water = 70/30 (v/v)

Acetophenone	$10^5 k/s^{-1}$ at [Acetophenone]/M					
	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80	1.0
H	2.93	4.11	5.09	5.90	6.95	9.78
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	3.08	4.43	5.55	6.76	8.36	12.53
<i>p</i> -Cl	—	2.58	3.26	4.19	5.42	7.73

Effect of sulphuric acid : It is observed that the presence of sulphuric acid largely accelerates the rate of oxidation of acetophenones with selenium dioxide. The rate of reaction is further accelerated with increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid (Table 3). The plots of log k vs log $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ are linear having slopes of approximately unity except in case of *p*-methylacetophenone. This indicates that the reactions are first order in $[\text{H}^+]$ in case of acetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone, but fractional order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ in case of *p*-methylacetophenone.

The reaction rates are found to decrease with increase in pH of the reaction medium. In case of acetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone, the rate constant is found to decrease from 6.95×10^{-5} to $2.49 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 8.36×10^{-5} to $3.35 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 5.42×10^{-5} to $2.12 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, when the pH of the reaction mixture changes from 0.9 to 2.4 as a result of added sodium acetate, 0.00 to 0.20 M.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF H_2SO_4 ON THE REACTION RATE
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01\text{ M}$, [acetophenone] = 0.50 M, Temp. = 338 K,
 HOAc - water = 70/30 (v/v)

Acetophenone	$10^5 k/s^{-1}$ at [Sulphuric acid]/M					
	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
H	4.11	10.40	20.53	26.95	30.13	34.55
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	4.43	13.52	18.57	20.20	22.30	24.39
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.58	10.11	18.42	34.59	30.44	39.40

Primary salt effect : The primary salt effect of added K_2SO_4 on the reaction rate is nominal, retarding in dilute solution (Table 4). This suggests that at least one of the reacting species in the rate determining step is a neutral molecule¹⁸.

Effect of dielectric constant : The effect of dielectric constant of the reaction medium on the

TABLE 4—PRIMARY SALT EFFECT ON REACTION RATE
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01\text{ M}$, [acetophenone] = 0.80 M, Temp. = 338 K,
 HOAc - water = 70/30 (v/v)

Acetophenone	$10^5 k/s^{-1}$ at $[\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4]/\text{M}$				
	0.00	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.012
H	6.95	6.82	6.47	6.37	6.32
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	8.36	8.35	8.20	7.93	—
<i>p</i> -Cl	5.42	5.42	5.40	5.24	5.22

reaction rate was studied by varying the percentage of acetic acid. It is observed that the reaction rate increases with the increase in the percentage of acetic acid, that is, decreases in the dielectric constant of the reaction medium (Table 5). Plots of log k vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ are linear, suggesting the reactions to be dipole - dipole¹⁹.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT ON REACTION RATE

Acetophenone	$10^5 k/s^{-1}$ at HOAc - water ratio				
	65 : 35	70 : 30	75 : 25	80 : 20	85 : 15
H	—	6.95	9.45	13.76	19.32
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	5.83	8.36	12.35	18.32	—
<i>p</i> -Cl	3.55	5.42	9.29	16.15	28.92

Effect of temperature : From the specific rate constants at different temperatures, the activation parameters, enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*), were calculated (Table 6). The high negative entropy of activation is in consonance with rigid transition state. A constancy in free energy of activation ($\Delta G^* = 110 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) in the acetophenones, suggests that probably a similar type of mechanism prevails.

TABLE 6—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES WITH SELENIUM DIOXIDE

Acetophenone	$[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01\text{ M}$, [acetophenone] = 0.80 M, Temp. = 338 K, HOAc - water = 70/30 (v/v)		
	ΔH^* KJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^*$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
H	70.440	118.2	109.61 ± 0.68
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	72.692	108.8	109.46 ± 0.85
<i>p</i> -Cl	69.878	120.6	110.63 ± 0.88

Structure and reactivity : The observed order of reactivity among acetophenones studied is *p*-methylacetophenone > acetophenone > *p*-chloroacetophenone. This shows that the electron releasing group in benzene ring facilitates the oxidation and the electron withdrawing group retards the process. The electron releasing group donates the electron by resonance, thereby increases the relative stability of the keto form and hence higher reactivity. The Hammett plot of log k/k_0 vs σ_p^+ for the studied acetophenones is linear (Fig. 1) with a ρ value of -0.24. The negative value of ρ indicates that

Sharpless and Gordon²⁷ have suggested that the oxidation of ketones involves electrophilic attack of selenious acid on the enol to give an intermediate β -ketoseleninic acid. The latter on Pummerer like decomposition yields the α -diketone. These workers could not isolate the intermediate, but made an attempt to give an evidence regarding its generation. The present investigation rules out the possibility of electrophilic attack of selenious acid on the enol. Further, the ketol could not be identified, which indicates that Se^{IV} keto ester is not hydrolysed under the experimental conditions employed. Thus it can be concluded that the oxidation of acetophenones by selenium dioxide does not follow the mechanistic path suggested by Sharpless and Gordon²⁷.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. J. P. Schaefer, President, Research Corporation, Tucson, Arizona, for discussion and valuable suggestions.

References

1. F. R. DUKE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 419.
2. E. J. COREY and J. P. SCHAEFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 918.
3. J. P. SCHAEFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 713, 717.
4. K. J. SINGH and S. N. ANAND, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 363.
5. N. D. VALECHHA and A. PRADHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 495.
6. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and S. DEVI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 496.
7. N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 557.
8. N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATPATHY and P. L. NAYAK, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1973, **77**, 163.
9. P. L. NAYAK and N. C. KHANDUAL, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1979, **98**, 57.
10. G. O. MISHRA, B. K. SINHA and G. B. BEHERA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1053.
11. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and M. D. PRASAD RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 524.
12. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and M. D. PRASAD RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **17**, 60.
13. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and S. N. PATI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 319.
14. S. C. PATI and B. R. DEV, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 262.
15. P. MANIKYAMBA, P. RAGHUNATH RAO and E. V. SUNDARM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 652.
16. H. L. RILEY, J. F. MORLEY and N. A. C. FRIEND, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1875.
17. R. T. ARNOLD and R. O. FUSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1295.
18. J. N. BRONSTED, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 169.
19. E. S. AMIS, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1953, **30**, 351.
20. J. E. LEFFLER and E. GRUNWALD, 'Rates and Equilibria of Organic Reactions', Wiley, New York, 1963, pp. 324, 342.
21. J. P. SCHAEFER, B. HORVATH and H. P. KLIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 2647.
22. P. D. BARTLETT and C. H. STAUFFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 2580.
23. S. K. SHU, C. K. INGOLD and C. N. WILSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 78.
24. K. F. BONHOEFFER and O. REITZ, *Phys. Chem. A*, 1937, 179.
25. L. N. PATNAYAK, P. L. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 668.
26. N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATPATHY and P. L. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 770.
27. K. B. SHARPLESS and K. M. GORDON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 300.